

An Urgent Call (and Some Basic Indicators) to Restore the Night

Plenary Lecture

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Abstract: Light pollution research unveils the mechanisms through which artificial light at night (ALAN) distorts the natural patterns of life. As it frequently happens in the scientific endeavor, any new answer elicits dozens of new questions. The permanent stress between what we already know and what we still ignore is a wholesome dynamics, deeply woven in the fabric of science. The large number of issues deserving further research has contributed somehow to spread the opinion that our present knowledge is still insufficient for adopting large scale policies for light pollution control. It is also generally believed that the absence of standards for measuring and reporting light pollution prevents further steps in regulatory and executive actions. Here I argue that -from the scientific and technical points of view- we already have the basic conceptual and methodological tools required for the effective control of light pollution at multiple scales. Lack of political resolve, rather than lack of additional standards, appears to be the main bottleneck now. This of course doesn't detract from the need of pursuing strong research programs and developing new and updated standards where appropriate. Controlling ALAN is an urgent need. Biodiversity losses will not always be recovered by simply dimming the lights after the damage has already been done. Environmental generational amnesia plus shifting baselines may quickly erase social awareness on this issue. This talk briefly revisits the role of ALAN as a pollutant and discusses practical light pollution indicators that could be used today for elaborating efficient restoration plans.

Keywords: light pollution; artificial light at night (ALAN); environmental policy; biodiversity impact.

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